

Supplemental Materials

Appendix S1. Field data collection

We conducted field campaigns during 16–17 March 2025 (pre-monsoon) and 19–20 July 2025 (monsoon) to measure the water surface slope and discharge of the Ganga River between Chhapra and Patna (Fig. S1). The dates of these measurements coincide with the SWOT overpass (ascending pass 551 and descending pass 008). To measure along stream WSE profiles, we used a Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS-Geomax Zenith 35 Pro) in Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) mode. It can measure elevation with a vertical accuracy of $\pm 1\text{--}2$ cm. To ensure reliable satellite geometry and consistent positional corrections, we established two base stations: one at Sherpur village (25.7231°N, 84.8532°E) and another at Digha Ghat, Patna (25.6205°N, 85.1901°E) near #VS12. The base station can communicate with the rover for a distance of about 10 km. Each base station operated in static mode for 8–10 hours, logging data at 1 Hz to maintain stable corrections (Fig. S1).

Fig. S1. The Ganga River study reach between Chhapra and Patna. The map shows the SWOT satellite tracks, locations of DGPS base stations (circle in red), and WSE profiles (dotted lines in red and blue). The transects (in solid blue and red) in the upstream (before the confluence of the Sone to the Ganga)

and downstream (after the confluence of the Gandak to the Ganga) show the water discharge measurement locations.

To record WSE, we mounted the rover unit of DGPS vertically on the floor of a motorized boat that touched the water surface. The boat slowly drifted downstream and recorded the elevation of the water surface at 1-second intervals. We covered about 22 km of profile from the upstream (at the confluence of the Son and Ganga) on 16th March and 42 km during 19-20 July 2025. To measure discharge, we deployed an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) from Teledyne RD Instruments RioGrande 1.2 MHz. We measured discharge at two transects (one at upstream and one at downstream) where the river was flowing as a single channel (Fig. S1). Each transect was surveyed at least twice to quantify measurement uncertainty, with boat speed maintained at 1–2 m/s to ensure consistent ADCP data quality. This allowed measurement of the entire river flow passing through a cross-section.

Appendix S2. Field data processing

We transformed raw DGPS coordinates, recorded in WGS84 ellipsoidal heights, into orthometric heights using the EGM2008 geoid model to account for geoid height variations across the study reach. We then assessed errors by comparing rover positions to base station corrections, achieving a horizontal error of 2–4 cm and a vertical error averaging 4 cm (ranging from 2–9 cm). These DGPS profiles were then compared with SWOT water-surface elevation (WSE) data. We used the 100 m Raster, Version C product (pass 551, Cycle 29) and Version D products (pass 551, Cycle 35, and pass 008, Cycle 36) of SWOT passes of 16th March and 19-20 July 2025 to extract river WSE. The July 2025 SWOT data from pass 008 was analyzed exclusively for the tile coinciding with the field measurement reach, independent of the primary time-series analysis period

We noticed considerable scatter in the water surface elevation data obtained from the Version C product of SWOT. This is likely due to low flow conditions and mixed backscatter from exposed bars in the river. To filter out these outliers, we applied a Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) filter and calculated the median WSE. The MAD is the mean of the absolute deviations from the median and excludes data points beyond a threshold of the median plus or minus the MAD. We did not perform any post-processing on the Version D product, as the SWOT-measured WSE values were in good agreement with the in-situ measurements.

Appendix S3. Sensitivity Analysis of River hydraulic parameters

To analyze the impact of Manning's roughness coefficient (n) and lean-flow depth (h_0) for discharge estimation, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis was conducted using Manning's equation. The analysis evaluated four values of n (0.010, 0.015, 0.018, 0.022) and h_0 (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 m) across twelve virtual stations (#VS2–#VS16). Performance was assessed against GloFAS v4.0 reanalysis using Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE), root mean square error (RMSE), and coefficient of determination (R^2), with NSE and RMSE as the primary metrics. Rectangular (Equations 2–7) and parabolic (Equations 8–13) geometries were tested to assess robustness across morphologies, guided by a power-law framework for cross-section estimation (Equation 2; Mejia and Reed, 2011), including wetted perimeter and hydraulic radius. Reach-averaged results highlighted that, over deeper channel sections (>10 meter), use of rectangular channel geometry delivered strong performance (Fig. S2). With increasing lean flow depth, (h_0) and Manning's roughness coefficient (n) discharge estimation performance degraded. Better performance was observed at 0.5 m and 1 m depth with $n = 0.015$; however, at these ranges, RMSE remained high. Therefore, a depth of 1 m is a realistic value for deeper channels and $n = 0.018$ was found to be the best combination for discharge estimation with second-best RMSE value of 3946 m³/s. Over the Ghaghara River, the discharge estimation was done using parabolic cross sections. The seasonal flow depth variations also remained low as compared to the Ganga River, which reflects relatively shallow channel geometry. Reach-averaged results (Fig. S2) showed NSE peaking at low n and h_0 , declining with increasing n (elevated friction) or $h_0 > 1.0$ m. Based on the average NSE and RMSE ranges, it was found that discharge estimation was optimal for 1 m of depth and $n = 0.018$ (Fig. S3). However, using a combination of published hydraulic literature, limited targeted field campaigns, and observed river morphology, this study demonstrates that it is possible to prescribe physically reasonable Manning's n and lean flow depth (h_0) values without local gauge-based calibration. In practical SWOT applications, users must in any case assume some values for these parameters; the proposed framework shows that choosing n and h_0 from literature-supported ranges and channel characteristics (e.g., planform, bed material, and depth variability) derived from limited field data or satellite observations yields robust discharge estimates over stable reaches. Under this framework, the method does not depend on fixed gauges and is therefore transferable to ungauged basins, with gauges used only for evaluation in this study rather than for parameter tuning.

Fig. S2. Sensitivity analysis of reach averaged results using rectangular cross sections for discharge estimating using varying Manning's roughness coefficient (n) and lean flow depth (h_0).

Fig. S3. Sensitivity analysis of reach averaged results using parabolic cross section for discharge estimating using varying Manning's (n) and lean flow depth (h_0).

Table S1. Statistical performance of SWOT derived discharge for different virtual stations.

Virtual Station	SWOT Pass	Latitude	Longitude	Rectangular Section ($n=0.018$ and $h_0 = 1$ m)			Parabolic Section ($n=0.018$ and $h_0 = 1$ m)		
				NSE	R ²	RMSE (m ³ /sec)	NSE	R ²	RMSE (m ³ /sec)
#VS2	Pass-036 Track – 110R	25.16	82.50	0.65	0.88	2180	-	0.88	3780
#VS3		25.19	82.57	0.5	0.8	3130	-	0.80	4545
#VS4		25.23	82.62	0.85	0.88	2049	-	0.87	3594
#VS5		25.18	82.69	0.59	0.88	1713	-	0.82	3846
#VS6		25.12	82.79	0.76	0.80	2498	-	0.8	3481
#VS8		Pass-551 Track – 200L	25.15	82.88	0.28	0.75	7623	0.66	0.74
#VS9	26.14		83.87	0.64	0.87	3321	0.82	0.87	1419
#VS10	26.11		83.98	0.52	0.84	4364	0.82	0.84	1606
#VS11	26.07		84.12	0.74	0.9	2978	0.87	0.90	1188
#VS13	Pass-245 Track – 199L	26.00	84.21	0.94	0.95	3128	0.14	0.94	7345
#VS15	Pass-245 Track – 199R	25.93	84.30	0.59	0.75	7651	0.32	0.74	5943
#VS16		25.66	85.06	0.51	0.62	8127	0.56	0.61	4670

*Ghaghara tributary: #VS7 to #VS11, while remaining VS are over Ganga mainstream.

Fig. S4. Water level comparison from SWOT derived water surface elevation using different methods and gauge observations for the Virtual Station-6 (#VS6) over the Ganga River.

Fig. S5. Water level comparison from SWOT derived water surface elevation using different methods and gauge observations for the Virtual Station-9 (#VS9) over the Ghaghara River.

Fig. S6. Water level comparison between CWC Gauge vs SWOT at #VS9 and #VS11 (Ghaghara River).

Fig. S7. Water-surface elevation profiles for the July 2025. The plots compare high-resolution DGPS measurements (solid dots) against SWOT satellite data (hollow circles).

Fig. S8. Comparison of GloFAS model discharge against SWOT-derived discharge using parabolic cross section geometry for a virtual station over the Ghaghara River (#VS10 [A, B]).